

The ten months in the primitive Roman calendar

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This discussion is concerning the literature about the number of months in the primitive Roman calendar, which, according to the myth, was stated by Romulus. It could have been made of ten months or of twelve. But, this is not the only concern of the proposed discussion. The aim is also that of noting an interesting fact about the mourning for widows, which in origin was of ten months, then changed into twelve months.

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It seems that two main theories exist about the number of months in the primitive Roman calendar. A theory tells that it was of ten months, the other of twelve¹. The calendar having ten months in a year is usually referred to as the supposed calendar traditionally stated by Romulus, the founder of Rome. In the article the link of which is given in Footnote 1, I contributed with some discussion about the names and numbers of months. Actually, about the Roman calendar, I made a study concerning the reform operated by Julius Caesar [1]. This study was based on the use of an astronomical software. In the case of the primitive Roman calendar, however, it is not easy to apply the software in order to recover a significant result. Of course it is possible, but it could be just a simulation, without any link to specific data.

In any case, a reader could be curious to understand who supported the theory of the ten or of the twelve months. We can help us with the item² about the Roman calendar in the Dictionary of Greek and Roman Antiquities, 1875, having William Smith as editor. The section on the Roman calendar was written by Thomas Hewitt Key. So, let us stop to the ancient literature, not reporting modern and recent results. This is a research, requiring the analysis of all the scholar literature and it will be proposed in a future article.

The text by Thomas Hewitt Key is rich of references to ancient literature.

He is mentioning the Year of Romulus. It is told that Romulus is commonly linked to the calendar, or better, that the "year" in the earliest times of Rome was linked to him. As stressed by Hewitt Key, what we find in the ancient literature is not consistent with

1 <https://www.livescience.com/november-months-roman-calendar.html> - 16 November 2020.

2 http://penelope.uchicago.edu/Thayer/E/Roman/Texts/secondary/SMIGRA*/Calendarium.html

regard to the form of this year. "The historians Licinius Macer and Fenestella maintained that the oldest year consisted of twelve months, and that it was already in those days an *annus vertens*, that is, a year which coincided with the period of the sun's course. Censorinus, however, in whose work this statement occurs ..., goes on to say that more credit is due to Graccanus, Fulvius (Nobilior), Varro, and others, according to whom the Romans in the earliest times, like the people of Alba from whom they sprang, allotted to the year but ten months. This opinion is supported by Ovid in several passages of his *Fasti* (I.27, I. 43, III.99, 119, 151); by Gellius (*Noct. Att.* III.16), Macrobius (*Saturn.* I.12), Solinus (*Polyh.* I), and Servius (*ad Georg.* I.43). Lastly, an old Latin year of ten months is implied in the fact, that at Laurentum (*Macrob.* I.15) a sacrifice was offered to Juno Kalendaris on the first of every month except February and January".

In fact, I am very fond of Varro, in particular for his description of seasons [2]. From this Latin author, I learnt many facts about the Roman subdivision of the year in seasons by means of the cross-quarter days, which is still in use among people of Celtic origin, but also in Italy in some local traditions too.

Let us continue with the item in the Dictionary. "These ten months were called Martius, Aprilis, Maius, Junius, Quinctilis, Sextilis, September, October, November, December. That March was the first month in the year is implied in the last six names; and even Plutarch, who ascribes twelve months to the Romulian year (Numa, c18), places Januarius and Februarius at the end. The fact is also confirmed by the ceremony of rekindling the sacred fire in the temple of Vesta on the first day of March, by the practice of placing fresh laurels in the public buildings on that day, and by many other customs recorded by Macrobius (I.12). With regard to the length of the months, Censorinus, Macrobius, and Solinus agree in ascribing thirty-one days to four of them, called *pleni menses*; thirty to the rest called *cavi menses*. The four longer months were Martius, Maius, Quinctilis, and October; and these, as Macrobius observes, were distinguished in the latest form of the Roman calendar by having their *nones* two days later than any of the other months. The symmetry of this arrangement will appear by placing the numbers in succession: 31, 30; 31, 30; 31, 30, 30; 31, 30, 30. Ovid, indeed, appears to speak of the months as coinciding with the lunar period, [that is] *Annus erat decimum cum luna repleverat annum*".

"A poet must not be pressed too closely", tells Thomas Hewitt Key. "On the other hand, Plutarch, in the passage already referred to, while he assigns to the old year twelve months and 365 days, speaks of the months as varying without system between the limits of twenty and thirty-five days. Such an irregularity is not incredible, as we find that even when Censorinus wrote (A.D. 238), the Alban calendar gave 36 days to March, 22 to May, 18 to Sextilis, and 16 to September; while at Tusculum Quinctilis had 36 days, October 32; and again at Aricia the same month, October, had no less than 39 (Censorinus). The Romulian year, if we follow the majority of authors, contained but 304 days; a period differing so widely from the real length of the sun's course, that the

months would rapidly revolve through all the seasons of the year. This inconvenience was remedied, says Macrobius, by the addition of the proper number of days required to complete the year; but these days, he goes on to say, did not receive any name as a month. Servius speaks of the intercalated period as consisting of two months, which at first had no name, but were eventually called after Janus and Februus. That some system of intercalation was employed in the Romulian year, was also the opinion of Licinius Macer (Macrob. I.13). This appears to be all that is handed down with regard to the earliest year of the Romans".

And now, about the truth of tradition.

"As a year of ten months and 304 days, at once falls greatly short of the solar year, and contains no exact number of lunations, some have gone so far as to dispute the truth of the tradition in whole or in part, while others have taxed their ingenuity to account for the adoption of so anomalous a year. Puteanus (De Nundinis, in Graevius' Thesaurus, vol. VIII), calling to mind that the old Roman or Etruscan week contained eight days, every eighth day being specially devoted to religious and other public purposes, under the name of nonae or nundinae, was the first to point out that number 304 is a precise multiple of eight. To this observation, in itself of little moment, Niebuhr³ has given some weight, by further noticing that the 38 nundines in a year of 304 days tally exactly with the number of dies fasti afterwards retained in the Julian calendar. Another writer, Pontedera, observed that ... ; and Niebuhr (Rom. Hist. vol. 1 p271), who is a warm advocate of the ten-month year, has made much use of this consideration. He thus explains the origin of the well-known quinquennial period called the lustrum, which Censorinus expressly calls an annus magnus, that is, in the modern language of chronology, a cycle. Moreover, the year of ten months, says the same writer (p.279), was the term for mourning, for paying portions left by will, for credit on the sale of yearly profits; most probably for all loans; and it was the measure for the most ancient rate of interest. Lastly, he finds in the existence of this short year the solution of certain historical difficulties. A peace, or rather truce, with Veii was concluded in the year 280 of Rome, for 40 years. In 316 Fidenae revolted and ... These facts are explained by supposing the years in question to have been those of ten months, for 40 of these are equal to 33 1/3 ordinary years, 20 to 16 2/3; so that the former truce terminated in 314, the latter in 346. Similarly, ..." And so on.

"These ingenious and perhaps satisfactory speculations of the German critic, of course imply that the decimестrial year still survived long after the regal government had ceased; and in fact he believes that this year, and the lunar year, as determined by

3 Barthold Georg Niebuhr (1776 – 1831) was a Danish–German statesman, banker, and historian who became Germany's leading historian of Ancient Rome. By 1810 Niebuhr was inspiring German patriotism in students at the University of Berlin by his analysis of Roman economy and government. Niebuhr was a leader of the Romantic era and symbol of German national spirit that emerged after the defeat at Jena. But he was also deeply rooted in the classical spirit of the Age of Enlightenment in his intellectual presuppositions, his use of philologic analysis, and his emphasis on both general and particular phenomena in history. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Barthold_Georg_Niebuhr

Scaliger's proposed cycle of 22 years, co-existed from the earliest times down to a late period. The views of Niebuhr do not require that the months should have consisted of 31 or 30 days; indeed it would be more natural to suppose that each month, as well as the year, contained a precise number of eight-day weeks; eight of the months, for instance, having four such weeks, the two others but three. Even in the so-called calendar of Numa we find the Etruscan week affecting the division of the month, there being eight days between the nones and ides, from which circumstances the nones received their name; and again two such weeks from the ides to the end of the month; and this, whether the whole month contained 31 or 29 days."

The dictionary then continues with the Year of Numa, therefore with the first supposed reform of the Roman calendar. Another interesting reference about the Roman calendar is the "Origines Kalendariae Italicae; Nundinal Calendars of Ancient Italy, Nundinal Calendar of Romulus, Calendar of Numa Pompilius, Calendar of the Decemvirs, Irregular Roman Calendar and Julian Correction; Tables of the Roman Calendar, in Four Volumes, Vol. IV", by Greswell, Edward, 1854, Oxford University Press (Oxford), available at <https://archive.org/details/dli.granth.107155/page/n9/mode/2up>

Today we are using a calendar which is coming from the Gregorian reform of the Julian Calendar. So, let us try to fill the gap between Romulus and Julius Caesar, with reading Ref. [3]. It is told that Julius Caesar's reform of the calendar replaced a pre-existing lunisolar calendar, known as the pre-Julian calendar, or also as the Republican Roman calendar. This calendar "has been the Roman state's method of marking the passage of time during the previous four hundred years and so on of the Republic. Nevertheless, ancient *testimonia* and the structure of the calendar itself suggest that the pre-Julian system was the third in an evolutionary process of early Roman time reckoning. During the last two centuries B.C. Roman antiquarians were of the opinion that Romulus", in his role of founder of Rome, had established a calendar, "but one of only ten months". His successor, Numa Pompilius, added two months. "Romulus began the year with March with the arrival of spring and had end with December and the onset of winter". Numa completed the cycle of the year by adding January and February.

In [3], it is also told the following. "Strange as Romulus' calendar may seem, in his world-wide survey of pre-literate peoples and their way of reckoning time Martin Nilsson⁴ encountered several similar cases in which a people did not bother assigning names to a season of the year characterized by prolonged heat and aridity or cold; and this notion received additional support and corroborations from Frazer's comparative examples⁵".

4 Martin Persson Nilsson (1874 – 1967) was a Swedish philologist, mythographer, and a scholar of the Greek, Hellenistic and Roman religious systems. In his studies he combined literary evidence with archaeological evidence, linking historic and prehistoric evidence for the evolution of the Greek mythological cycles.

5 Sir James George Frazer (1854 – 1941) was a Scottish social anthropologist and folklorist influential in the early stages of the modern studies of mythology and comparative religion. His most famous work, *The Golden Bough* (1890), documents and details the similarities among magical and religious

It is time to stop our preliminary report of literature. Let me just add a few links to books in Italian and an article [4-7].

In [6], we find an article written by Luigi Pedroni, (1998), entitled *Ipotesi sull'evoluzione del calendario arcaico di Roma*. Abstract tells that "In the pre-Julian Roman calendar there were two cycles of festivals to mark the end of the year, in December and in February, and also residual elements of the decimal scansion of Roman metrology. Together, these elements confirm the traditional hypothesis of a year composed of ten months (the so-called Romulian year) prior to that of twelve months (the so-called Numan year). The Romulian calendar was modified quite considerably during the times of the first Etruscan kings, associated with profound socio-political, and perhaps also metrological, reforms. From then, the two "missing" months in the "decimal" calendar, periods in which work would have been concentrated within the home rather than outside, with the exchange of the surpluses which had been accumulated, were incorporated. The new months were called Mercedonius and Februarius, the latter being the last month of the year. A radical revision of the calendar, which resulted in the last two months becoming the first two, appears to have occurred at the time of the dramatic move to the Republic, as the old festival was too closely related to the figure of the rex. It can be concluded that the archaic calendar of Rome reflects a stratified series of various religious, political and ideological elements evolving over the centuries".

And an astronomer too investigated the primitive calendar of Rome: *Storia del cielo per Camillo Flammarion*⁶, [7]. "Calippo rese il ciclo più esatto,... Il calendario romano, disse l'astronomo, era ancor più complicato del greco, e meno buono. È un vero *cafarnaum*⁷. Romolo diede a' suoi sudditi un bizzarro ordinamento, nel quale non possiamo intender più nulla. Più guerriero che scienziato, il fondatore di Roma faceva l'anno di soli 10 mesi, gli uni di 20 giorni, gli altri di 55. Queste durate inuguali erano probabilmente regolate dai lavori campestri e dalle idee religiose dominanti. Passati i dieci mesi, ricominciavasi a contare ...". Romolo, più guerriero che scienziato.

After this short, very short, survey of literature, let us consider again the *Dictionary of Greek and Roman Antiquities*, 1875. In it we find mentioned that the time period of ten months was a legal period, and in particular, it "was the term for mourning". Let us be more specific, it was the term for mourning that widows had to observe.

From a discussion of *Pandette*⁸ [8]. "Le vedove, che durante l'anno di lutto si rimaritano

beliefs around the world. Frazer posited that human belief progressed through three stages: primitive magic, replaced by religion, in turn replaced by science.

6 Nicolas Camille Flammarion (1842 – 1925) was a French astronomer and author. He was a prolific author of more than fifty titles, including popular science works about astronomy, several notable early science fiction novels, and works on psychical research and related topics. He also published the magazine *L'Astronomie*, starting in 1882.

7 Capharnaum definition is - a confused jumble: a place marked by a disorderly accumulation of objects.

8 *Pandette*: Titolo di vaste trattazioni complessive del diritto romano pubblicate da alcuni dei maggiori

senza aver ottenuto dispensa e così pure coloro, che scientemente e volontariamente contraggono matrimonio con esse, diventano infami per il diritto romano. Si riteneva sempre in questo caso possibile, che la vedova si trovasse incinta del suo defunto marito e si temeva pertanto, come dice ULPIANO, una turbatio sanguinis in causa del precedente matrimonio, o, come GIUSTINIANO s'esprime, una incertitudo generationis o seminis. Non si può con fondamento negare che il timore di questa incertezza a riguardo del parto, [timore] che sorgerebbe col maritarsi della vedova subito dopo la morte del marito [era alla base di tale legge] ... la vedova originariamente non manteneva che per dieci mesi il lutto del marito, nonostante che l'anno del calendario romano già dopo Numa POMPILIO constasse i dodici mesi, perché già nei più antichi tempi - anzi - come GELLIO insegna - già nelle leggi delle Dodici Tavole fu elevato a principio aver luogo la nascita dell'uomo al più tardi dieci mesi dopo la concezione; che la vedova dovesse osservare in ogni caso il periodo legale del lutto ... [L'anticipo del matrimonio era inoltre una offesa alla morale ed all'onore]. Per tale ragione l'imperatore TEODOSIO il Grande commutò il periodo di dieci mesi di lutto della vedova in un intero anno".

The author added in a note that "Non entra nel proposito nostro insistere sulla inesattezza di queste idee, ormai abbandonate dalla critica⁹. Giovi però accennare come assai dubbia sia la natura di quell'antico anno cosiddetto romuleo: se non fosse cioè un vero anno, ma semplicemente un periodo di dieci mesi lunari (MOMMSEN, Cronologia romana, p. 52), ovvero se, pur corrispondendo ad un dipresso all'anno attuale per la durata, constasse di dieci assai rozze divisioni del tempo intercedente fra due primavere (IDELER, Manuale della cronologia matematica e tecnica, vol. II p. 28). Assoluta incertezza regna poi sull'aggiunta di due mesi lunari alle antiche divisioni, la stessa leggenda è incerta ed ora l'attribuisce a NUMA, ora invece a TARQUINIO; cfr. specialmente A. ROLANDO, Delle ere principali come fondamento della cronologia storica, p. 30."

Then this is a small part of what we can find about the primitive calendar of ten months in a year. Actually I have not defined myself as a supporter of the ten months per year (see Note 1); I have simply mentioned that - and ancient literature exists reporting about - the names of the months in today calendar are echoes of a primitive time when the year was counted starting from March. Am I supporting the theory of the ten months in a year? May be, but because of it as a legal time period.

To conclude, let me made a short observation about the year of ten months required in the mourning for widows. What about the widowers? I cannot answer. But I guess it was as told by my grandmother: "Il lutto per la moglie morta dura dall'uscio alla porta".

giureconsulti dell'antichità, come Ulpiano o Modestino. Per antonomasia, secondo nome di quella parte del Corpus iuris civilis di Giustiniano che comprende la raccolta degli iura. www.treccani.it - Pandettistica: Movimento di scienza giuridica tedesca che, dalla fine del 18° sec. a tutto il 19°, si basò sui testi del diritto romano, onde si parlò appunto di usus modernus Pandectarum.

9 As we have seen, in literature we can find reappraisal of the primitive calendar.

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